

Supplementary Material

Persistent gene flow suggests an absence of reproductive isolation in an African antelope speciation model

Xi Wang^{*1}, Casper-Emil Tingskov Pedersen^{*2}, Georgios Athanasiadis^{1,3}, Genis Garcia-Erill¹, Kristian Hanghøj¹, Laura D. Bertola¹, Malthe Sebro Rasmussen¹, Mikkel Schubert⁷, Xiaodong Liu¹, Zilong Li¹, Long Lin¹, Renzo F. Balboa¹, Emil Jørsboe^{7,8,9}, Casia Nursyifa¹, Shanlin Liu⁶, Vincent Muwanika⁴, Charles Masembe⁵, Lei Chen¹⁰, Wen Wang¹⁰, Ida Moltke¹, Hans R. Siegismund¹, Anders Albrechtsen^{†1}, Rasmus Heller^{†1}

¹ *Department of Biology, University of Copenhagen, Ole Maaløes Vej 5, 2200 Copenhagen N, Denmark*

² *COPSAC, Copenhagen Prospective Studies on Asthma in Childhood, Herlev and Gentofte Hospital, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark*

³ *Department of Evolutionary Biology, Ecology and Environmental Sciences, University of Barcelona, 08028 Barcelona, Spain*

⁴ *Department of Environmental Management, Makerere University, PO Box 7062, Kampala, Uganda*

⁵ Department of Biology, Makerere University, PO Box 7062, Kampala, Uganda

⁶ Department of Entomology, College of Plant Protection, China Agricultural University, Beijing 100193, China

⁷ Novo Nordisk Foundation Center for Basic Metabolic Research, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Copenhagen, Denmark

⁸ Big Data Institute, Li Ka Shing Centre for Health Information and Discovery, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

⁹ Nuffield Department of Population Health, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

¹⁰ School of Ecology and Environment, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an 710072, China

* Contributed equally

† Corresponding / Senior authors: albrecht@binf.ku.dk; rheller@bio.ku.dk

Supplementary Text 1: Sampling, sequencing and mapping

Sample collection

A total of 145 samples (Dataset WaterA) were collected between 1992 and 1998 from 10 localities within the waterbuck distribution range (Fig. 1a; Supplementary Table 1). Two of them, Nairobi and Samburu, are known to harbor individuals of intermediate phenotypes (Williams 1967; Wilson 1989; Lorenzen et al. 2006).

We also included a single sample from each of six closely related species within the antelope tribe Reduncini: the mountain reedbuck (*Redunca fulvorufula*) and southern reedbuck (*R. arundinum*); the Senegal (*Kobus kob kob*), white-eared (*K. k. leucotis*) and Uganda kob (*K. k. thomasi*) and the puku (*Kobus vardoni*). Additionally, we downloaded publicly available whole genome sequencing data from a Bohor reedbuck (*R. redunca*) and a

red lechwe (*Kobus leche leche*) generated as part of the Ruminant Genome Project (Chen et al. 2019).

Lab Protocol

Samples consisting of skin tissue, biopsies or ear nicks were kept in a DMSO buffer in the field, stored at -20 °C as soon as possible, and were further transferred to a -80 °C freezer for long-term storage. The QIAGEN DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (QIAGEN, Valencia, CA, USA) was used for DNA extraction, following the manufacturer's protocol. RNase A was subsequently added to get RNA-free genomic DNA. Before using gel electrophoresis to check the quality of the genomic DNA, we further measured the DNA concentrations with a Qubit 2.0 Fluorometer and a Nanodrop. After DNA extraction, 1 mg genomic DNA was fragmented by Covaris (350 bp on average), followed by purification by AxyPrep Mag PCR clean up kit. The fragments were end-repaired by End Repair Mix and then purified. The repaired DNA was combined with A-Tailing Mix, then the Illumina adaptors were ligated to the DNA adenylate 3' ends, followed by product purification. Size selection was performed targeting insert sizes of 350 base pairs. Several rounds of PCR amplification with PCR Primer Cocktail and PCR Master Mix were performed to enrich the adaptor-ligated DNA fragments. After purification, the libraries were assessed by the Agilent Technologies 2100 Bioanalyzer and ABI StepOnePlus Realtime PCR System.

Sequencing

All samples were sequenced to approximately average 3.4X depth of coverage using Illumina paired-end 150 bp reads on Illumina's HiSeq 2000 platform. The two downloaded samples (Bohor reedbuck and red lechwe) were sequenced to much higher depths of 91.2X to 94.0X. We assessed the quality of the raw reads using FastQC (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>) and MultiQC (Ewels et al. 2016) before mapping.

Mapping

For mapping, we used a modified version of PALEOMIX 'bam' pipeline (Schubert et al. 2014, <https://github.com/xiqtcacf/WaterbuckScripts>), which is a pipeline designed for the processing of demultiplexed high-throughput short-read sequencing data.

We first trimmed Illumina universal adapters using AdapterRemoval v2.3.2 (Schubert et al. 2016). No trimming of low-quality bases and ambiguous bases (Ns) was performed. We merged overlapping paired-end reads into a single sequence with default parameters in order to improve the fidelity of the overlapping region by selecting the highest quality base when mismatches are observed. Mismatching positions in the alignment where both bases had the same quality were set to 'N' via the '--collapse-conservatively' option. Finally, empty reads resulting from trimming primer-dimers were removed.

We then used BWA mem v0.7.17-r1188 (Li 2013) to map the reads to: 1) a scaffold-level *defassa waterbuck* draft genome (Chen et al. 2019), and 2) the chromosome-level reference genome from a male San Clemente goat (ARS1; GenBank: GCA_001704415.1). PCR duplicates were flagged using samtools v1.11 'markdup' for paired reads and PALEOMIX 'rmdup_collapsed' for merged reads.

The resulting BAM files were merged and filtered based on standard BAM flags to exclude unmapped reads, reads with unmapped mate reads, secondary alignments, reads that failed QC, PCR duplicates, and supplementary alignments. In addition, we excluded reads with filtered mate reads, and reads in alignments with inferred insert sizes smaller than 50 bp or greater than 1000 bp, reads where fewer than 50 bp or less than 50% of the read were aligned, and read pairs in which mates mapped to different contigs or not in the expected orientation. Statistics of the filtered BAM files were generated by samtools 'stats' and 'idxstats' (Li et al. 2009).

Supplementary Text 2: Sample filtering

Basic mapping statistics filtering

We first evaluated statistics gathered as part of the BAM filtering step described above, including insert size distributions, mapping rates, average coverage, and the number of reads excluded based on each filtering criteria. The quality of all BAM files were further assessed using FastQC (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>) and MultiQC (Ewels et al. 2016) as post-mapping quality checking. We also evaluated the depth distribution per sample by using ANGSD (-doCounts1 -doDepth1) (Korneliussen et al. 2014, <https://github.com/ANGSD/angsd>). Sample 1219 and Sample 2589 were removed because of the extremely low mapping rate (<0.1%) (Supplementary Table 2).

Error rates

Sample sequencing error rates were measured using the 'perfect individual' method (Orlando et al. 2013) implemented in ANGSD, as excess mismatches between each sample and the outgroup (Goat reference), relative to the mismatches between the outgroup and a consensus sequence of a high depth sample, the 'perfect individual' (sample 1133). The idea is that each ingroup sample should have the same expected number of derived alleles as the 'perfect individual' when using an outgroup, and that a surplus of observed derived alleles in each sample is thus due to excess errors relative to the 'perfect individual'. A consensus sequence was first created for the 'perfect individual' using '-doCounts 1 -doFasta 2' option in ANGSD, and error rates were then estimated using all bases (-doAncError 1). For generating the consensus sequence and for the error estimation, we used quality filters including a minimum base quality of 20 and minimum mapping quality of 30. Based on this, sample 2553 showed extremely high error rate (1.34%), samples 7543, 7544 and 7593 showed relatively high error rates (0.10-0.43%), and four samples showed numerically large negative error rates: 7398, 7399, 7400, 7401 ([-0.03]-[-0.02%]), indicative

of being phylogenetically closer to the outgroup than the 'perfect individual'. These individuals were removed from downstream analyses (Supplementary Table 2).

Heterozygosity

We calculated site allele frequency likelihood based on individual genotype likelihoods assuming Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) for all samples using `-doSaf 1` in ANGSD. A per-individual site frequency spectrum (SFS) was estimated by `realSFS` in ANGSD. Based on individual SFS, the genome-wide heterozygosity for all samples was finally calculated by dividing the estimated number of heterozygous sites by the total number of sites. Two samples (1244 and 7321) showed extremely high values of heterozygosity and were consequently removed from further analyses (Supplementary Table 2).

Duplicates filtering based on King calculated from global 2D-sfs

Using the methodology described in Waples et al. (2019), we identified closely related and potentially duplicated samples by first inferring the two-dimensional site frequency spectrum (2d-SFS) for each pair of samples. Three statistics were then calculated directly from the 2d-SFS for each pair of samples: R_0 , R_1 , and the KING-robust kinship coefficient. These can be used to identify close familial relatives without the need to estimate population allele frequencies. We identified 14 duplicate pairs with KING-robust kinship values > 0.330 , and proceeded to exclude all but one sample from set of duplicated pairs (samples 7597, 7595, 7594, 1614_1, 1615_1, 2997, 1612, 397, Supplementary Table 2). For a few analyses (see Results) we chose to instead combine all data from each duplicated individual to achieve higher sequencing depth, which allowed us to validate the findings from the low depth data.

Relatedness filtering based on NgsRelate results within each location

Before downstream analyses, we performed a second and more sensitive analysis of relatedness within each sampling location by using NgsRelate, which can be used to infer relatedness for pairs of individuals from low coverage Next Generation Sequencing (NGS)

data by using genotype likelihoods instead of called genotypes (Korneliusson and Moltke 2015; Hanghøj et al. 2019). We first generated a file with allele frequencies (-doMaf 1) and a file with genotype likelihoods (-doGlf 3) for all samples (Dataset B) passing sample filtering and sites filtering criteria using ANGSD, with additional filtering of -hwe_pval 1e-6 -minmaf 0.05 -minMapQ 30 -minQ 20 -SNP_pval 1e-6. The frequency column from the allele frequency file was then extracted and used together with the genotype likelihood file by NgsRelate. We identified six additional pairs of relatives within the sampling localities Samole ($K1 > 0.15$ and $K2 > 0.8$), Matetsi ($K1 > 0.8$), and Ugalla ($K1 > 0.39$ and $K2 > 0.15$), and removed the lower depth sample from each pair (removing 7600, 7602 in Samole; 1597, 1607 in Matetsi; and 5620 in Ugalla, Supplementary Figure 1).

Supplementary Text 3: Sites filtering

Reference filtering: mappability, repeats and sex-linked scaffolds

The mappability of each site of both internal and external reference genomes were estimated by GenMap (v1.2.0) (Pockrandt et al. 2020), conservatively using 150bp k-mers with up to 2 mismatches (-K 150 -E 2) and defaults for the remaining settings. All sites with a mappability score less than one were excluded. We also discarded low complexity and repeat sequences in both reference fasta files using RepeatMasker v.4.1.1 (<http://www.repeatmasker.org/>). To identify sex-linked and abnormal scaffolds in the defassa waterbuck reference, we used SATC (Nursyifa et al. 2022). This resulted in 437 scaffolds being identified as X chromosome-linked and excluded from further analyses. In addition, we also removed all scaffolds smaller than 100 kb when using defassa waterbuck as reference. For the chromosome level goat reference, we only retained the 29 autosomal chromosomes (Supplementary Table 3). Additionally, sample sex was inferred when performing SATC, by showing the normalized depth of sex-linked scaffolds for each sample: depth of 0.5 as heterogametic samples (male) and depth of 1.0 as homogametic samples (female, Supplementary Figure 2).

Global depth filtering

We estimated global depth per site across all samples using ANGSD. We then estimated the mean and median depth per site across data sets and an average pooled depth across all individuals, and further excluded all sites that had a global depth below 375 (average depth * total number of samples) or above 1.5 times the median (655.5).

Excess heterozygosity (HWE) filtering

Mapping of repetitive DNA sequences to a reference genome creates ambiguous mapping of reads originating from multiple genome locations to a single location, resulting in sites with an excess of heterozygosity. Regions of extreme heterozygosity are indicative of such problematic mapping. We filtered such regions by first estimating genotype likelihoods for all waterbuck samples that passed the above sample quality control, using ANGSD with the GATK genotype likelihood model and basic quality filters (-SNP_pval 1e-6 -minmaf 0.05 -minMapQ 30 -minQ 20). Using these genotype likelihoods as input to PCAngsd (Meisner and Albrechtsen 2018, 2019), we then calculated the per-site inbreeding coefficients (F), ranging from -1 where all samples are heterozygous to 1 where all samples are homozygous, and performed a Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) likelihood ratio test accounting for population structure. The optimal number of principal components to model the population structure was inferred based on Velicer's minimum average partial test (Velicer 1976) implemented in PCAngsd. Finally, we treated sites with $F < -0.9$ and $p\text{-value} < 1e-6$ as excessively heterozygous and conservatively excluded all sites within 10kb of such sites. We did this for both data sets, mapped to defassa waterbuck and goat reference (Supplementary Table 3).

References

Chen L., Qiu Q., Jiang Y., Wang K., Lin Z., Li Z., Bibi F., Yang Y., Wang J., Nie W., Su W., Liu G., Li Q., Fu W., Pan X., Liu C., Yang J., Zhang C., Yin Y., Wang Y., Zhao Y., Zhang C., Wang Z., Qin

- Y., Liu W., Wang B., Ren Y., Zhang R., Zeng Y., da Fonseca R.R., Wei B., Li R., Wan W., Zhao R., Zhu W., Wang Y., Duan S., Gao Y., Zhang Y.E., Chen C., Hvilsom C., Epps C.W., Chemnick L.G., Dong Y., Mirarab S., Siegismund H.R., Ryder O.A., Gilbert M.T.P., Lewin H.A., Zhang G., Heller R., Wang W. 2019. Large-scale ruminant genome sequencing provides insights into their evolution and distinct traits. *Science*. 364(6446):eaav6202. doi: 10.1126/science.aav6202
- Ewels P., Magnusson M., Lundin S., Källér M. 2016. MultiQC: summarize analysis results for multiple tools and samples in a single report. *Bioinformatics*. 32:3047–3048.
- Hanghøj K., Moltke I., Andersen P.A., Manica A., Korneliussen T.S. 2019. Fast and accurate relatedness estimation from high-throughput sequencing data in the presence of inbreeding. *Gigascience*. 8 (5), giz034.
- Korneliussen T.S., Albrechtsen A., Nielsen R. 2014. ANGSD: Analysis of Next Generation Sequencing Data. *BMC Bioinformatics*. 15:356.
- Korneliussen T.S., Moltke I. 2015. NgsRelate: a software tool for estimating pairwise relatedness from next-generation sequencing data. *Bioinformatics*. 31:4009–4011.
- Li H., Handsaker B., Wysoker A., Fennell T., Ruan J., Homer N., Marth G., Abecasis G., Durbin R., 1000 Genome Project Data Processing Subgroup. 2009. The Sequence Alignment/Map format and SAMtools. *Bioinformatics*. 25:2078–2079.
- Li H. 2013. Aligning sequence reads, clone sequences and assembly contigs with BWA-MEM. Available from <https://arxiv.org/abs/1303.3997>
- Lorenzen E.D., Simonsen B.T., Kat P.W., Arctander P., Siegismund H.R. 2006. Hybridization between subspecies of waterbuck (*Kobus ellipsiprymnus*) in zones of overlap with limited introgression. *Mol. Ecol.* 15:3787–3799.
- Meisner J., Albrechtsen A. 2018. Inferring Population Structure and Admixture Proportions in Low-Depth NGS Data. *Genetics*. 210:719–731.
- Meisner J., Albrechtsen A. 2019. Testing for Hardy–Weinberg equilibrium in structured populations using genotype or low-depth next generation sequencing data. *Mol. Ecol. Resour.* 19:1144–1152.
- Nursyifa C., Brüniche-Olsen A., Garcia-Erill G., Heller R., Albrechtsen A. 2022. Joint identification of sex and sex-linked scaffolds in non-model organisms using low depth sequencing data. *Mol. Ecol. Resour.* 22:458–467.

- Orlando L., Ginolhac A., Zhang G., Froese D., Albrechtsen A., Stiller M., Schubert M., Cappellini E., Petersen B., Moltke I., Johnson P.L.F., Fumagalli M., Vilstrup J.T., Raghavan M., Korneliussen T., Malaspina A.-S., Vogt J., Szklarczyk D., Kelstrup C.D., Vinther J., Dolocan A., Stenderup J., Velazquez A.M.V., Cahill J., Rasmussen M., Wang X., Min J., Zazula G.D., Seguin-Orlando A., Mortensen C., Magnussen K., Thompson J.F., Weinstock J., Gregersen K., Røed K.H., Eisenmann V., Rubin C.J., Miller D.C., Antczak D.F., Bertelsen M.F., Brunak S., Al-Rasheid K.A.S., Ryder O., Andersson L., Mundy J., Krogh A., Gilbert M.T.P., Kjær K., Sicheritz-Ponten T., Jensen L.J., Olsen J.V., Hofreiter M., Nielsen R., Shapiro B., Wang J., Willerslev E. 2013. Recalibrating Equus evolution using the genome sequence of an early Middle Pleistocene horse. *Nature*. 499:74–78.
- Pockrandt C., Alzamel M., Iliopoulos C.S., Reinert K. 2020. GenMap: ultra-fast computation of genome mappability. *Bioinformatics*. 36:3687–3692.
- Schubert M., Ermini L., Der Sarkissian C., Jónsson H., Ginolhac A., Schaefer R., Martin M.D., Fernández R., Kircher M., McCue M., Willerslev E., Orlando L. 2014. Characterization of ancient and modern genomes by SNP detection and phylogenomic and metagenomic analysis using PALEOMIX. *Nat. Protoc.* 9:1056–1082.
- Schubert M., Lindgreen S., Orlando L. 2016. AdapterRemoval v2: rapid adapter trimming, identification, and read merging. *BMC Res. Notes*. 9:88.
- Velicer W.F. 1976. Determining the number of components from the matrix of partial correlations. *Psychometrika*. 41:321–327.
- Waples R.K., Albrechtsen A., Moltke I. 2019. Allele frequency-free inference of close familial relationships from genotypes or low-depth sequencing data. *Mol. Ecol.* 28:35–48.
- Williams JG. 1967. *A Field Guide to the National Parks of East Africa*. London: Collins.
- Wilson A. 1989. *Samburu, Buffalo Springs and Shaba National Reserves: A Visitor's Guidebook*. Kenya: Friends of Conservation.

Supplementary Materials Figures

Supplementary Figure 1. Estimates of relatedness for waterbucks within each sampling location by NGSrelate. Six pairs of relatives within the sampling localities Samole, Matetsi, and Ugalla were identified (pointed by arrows), and the lowest coverage sample in each pair was removed (removing 7600 and 7602 in Samole, both of which repeat twice in three pairs; 1597, 1607 in Matetsi; and 5620 in Ugalla).

Supplementary Figure 2. Boxplot of normalized depth of sex-linked scaffolds for each sample. The samples are ordered based on the two inferred sex groups identified by the Graphical User Interface (GUI) version of SATC. Expected values for each group are shown by horizontal green dashed lines of 0.5 (heterogametic) and 1.0 (homogametic). The vertical line separates the inferred heterogametic and homogametic samples.

Common

Defassa

Supplementary Figure 3. Linkage-disequilibrium decay for two subspecies along chromosome 1, described as mean r^2 values over distance of 0-5 Mb.

Supplementary Figure 4. PCA plot of waterbuck samples colored by sampling locality on the first ten principal components inferred with PCAngsd.

Supplementary Figure 5. Individual admixture proportions estimated with NGSadmix assuming from K = 2 to K = 10. Individuals are grouped by sampling locality.

Supplementary Figure 7. Neighbor-joining tree based on an identity-by-state (IBS) matrix of a, 108 individuals (WaterC) and 8 outgroups and b, 119 individuals (WaterB, recently admixed samples highlighted by adding a star) and 8 outgroups. IBS was calculated in ANGSD and processed using the R package *ape* version 5.6-2 (Paradis and Schliep 2019).

Heterozygosity for waterbuck populations

Supplementary Figure 8. Heterozygosity estimation using 108 waterbuck individuals without recently admixed samples based on genotype likelihoods (boxplots and small circles). The star symbols show the heterozygosity estimation based on called genotypes from high-depth individuals achieved by merging read data from duplicated samples. The overall similarity of estimates shows that the results are robust. The vertical line represents the split between subspecies; common waterbuck populations on the left and defassa waterbuck populations on the right.

Supplementary Figure 9. Global genetic differentiation measured as F_{st} values using Hudson's estimator between all population pairs estimated from the corresponding 2d-SFS.

Supplementary Figure 10. a, Schematic diagram depicting the fastsimcoal2 demographic model and parameter point estimates, when considering a simple divergence model without gene flow (NULL-model), a model with continuous gene flow from divergence to the present (IM-model), and a model with temporary gene flow following divergence (MStop-model). b, maximum likelihood for 100 runs of each model. c, the best model selection based on AIC and model normalized relative likelihood calculation. ^d Based on the best likelihood among the 100 independent runs for each model. ^e The calculation of AIC_i, Δ_i and w_i are according

to the methods shown in Excoffier et al. (2013).^f The best-fitting model was chosen based on 'Model normalized relative likelihood (w_i)' ≈ 1 . The Samole population was used to represent defassa waterbuck and Matetsi was used to represent common waterbuck. All inferred demographic parameters and 95% confidence intervals for the best model are shown in Supplementary Table 5, Supplementary Table 6 and Supplementary Table 7.

Supplementary Figure 11. D-statistics when using Bohor reedbuck as outgroup P4, various defassa waterbuck population pairs as P1, P2 and various common waterbuck populations as P3. The label in each row thereby denotes different combinations of populations in the

order P1-P2-P3. D-statistics were estimated by single read sampling for all possible combinations of samples within the population trio using ANGSD. Red points represent a significant P value after Bonferroni correction calculated from Z scores.

Supplementary Figure 12. Same plot with Supplementary Figure 11 by additional highlighting D-statistics between 11 recently admixed samples with other individuals.

Supplementary Figure 13. As Supplementary Figure 11, but using Bohor reedback as outgroup P4, various common waterbuck populations as P1, P2 and various defassa waterbuck as P3. Red points represent the significant P value after Bonferroni correction calculated from Z scores.

Supplementary Figure 14. Same plot with Supplementary Figure 13 by additional highlighting D-statistics between 11 recently admixed samples with other individuals.

Supplementary Figure 15. The proportion of the 15 possible topologies in 100kb windows across the autosomal genome for five taxa, combining Nairobi+Samuru into one taxon (NorthCom); Matetsi+Luangwa into another taxon (SouthCom); Maswa+KVNP+QENP+Ugalla into another (CentralDef); and treating Kafue and Samole as separate taxa. Here we show the topology proportions along windows on chromosome 2 as an example.

Supplementary Figure 16. Plot of F_{st} between two subspecies and variation in local topological relationships between two subspecies using TWISST (black as the proportion of merged weights of topologies consistent with subspecies monophyly among all 15 five-population topologies, and other colors represent remaining topology shown in Supplementary Figure 15), pairwise diversity, Tajima's D, and the pattern of localized linkage disequilibrium (LD) for defassa waterbuck (orange) and common waterbuck (light purple) of all 11 chromosomes where differentiation islands were found.

Supplementary Figure 17. Scatterplots of Twisst, pairwise nucleotide diversity versus F_{st} across the waterbuck whole genome. The Spearman correlation coefficient (r) is shown in the top right of each plot and the best-fitting regression lines are depicted in black line.

Supplementary Figure 18. Plot of F_{st} within all 14 outlying F_{st} windows and its surrounding genomic region, together with its annotated protein coding genes.

Supplementary Figure 19. Scatterplots of pairwise nucleotide diversity of each subspecies versus Dxy across the waterbuck whole genome. The Spearman correlation coefficient (r) is

shown in the top right of each plot and the best-fitting regression lines are depicted in black line.

Supplementary Figure 20. No signatures for reduced gene flow in 14 differentiation islands. From left to right: population structure within each divergence island inferred by PCAngsd; the information of subspecies and populations that grouped individuals based on 5 bins split by PC1 in A belonging to; and heterozygosity estimation using realSFS in ANGSD by grouping individuals based on 5 bins split by PC1 in A.

Supplementary Figure 21. Evaluation of binning three clusters by visual inspection of PC1 in the PCA for differentiation island is qualitative properly using admixture analysis (K=2). From top to bottom: population structure of divergence island within Chromosome 7 inferred by PCAngsd; admixture of divergence island within Chromosome 7 inferred by NGSadmix.

Supplementary Figure 22. No signatures for reduced gene flow in 14 differentiation islands when adding 11 recently admixed individuals identified by NGSadmix. a. Population structure within each divergence island inferred by PCAngsd and b. heterozygosity estimation using realSFS in ANGSD by grouping individuals based on 5 bins split by PC1 in A.

Supplementary Figure 23. Highlighting D-statistics values of 10 “disparate” samples identified in Supplementary Figure 20.

Supplementary Figure 24. Average Fst across each chromosome.

Supplementary Figure 25. Identification of two possible divergence islands on the X chromosome, using the distribution of F_{st} across windows on the X chromosomal scaffolds to define top 0.1% outlier windows. Blue color in the plot of TWISST represents the proportion of merged weights of topologies consistent with subspecies monophyly among all 15 five-population topologies, and other colors represent remaining topology shown in Supplementary Figure 15.

Supplementary Materials Tables

Supplementary Table 1. Data sets after different steps of quality control.

Population	Original samples	Passed samples QC	Passed samples QC and removing 11 recently admixed samples
Samole	26	13	13
Maswa	7	7	7
KVNP	7	5	5
QENP	15	15	14
Ugalla	21	19	16
Kafue	15	12	12
Samburu	18	17	12
Matetsi	23	18	18
Nairobi	9	9	7
Luangwa	4	4	4
Total	145	119	108
Dataset	WaterA ^a GoatA ^b	WaterB ^a GoatB ^b	WaterC ^a GoatC ^b

^a Dataset mapped to defassa waterbuck.

^b Dataset mapped to goat.

Supplementary Table 2. Sample inclusion after different steps of sample filtering.

Supplementary Table 3. Summary statistics for sites filtering.

	Defassa Waterbuck (ref)		Goat (ref)	
	88935 scaffolds sites:2895549025		29907 scaffolds sites:2922813246	
	sites removed	sites remained (proportion%)	sites removed	sites remained (proportion%)
Sex Linked And Abnormal Scaffolds	250'295'945	2'645'253'080 (91%)	133'653'460 (Keep 4Chr, so all 29 were maintained)	2'789'159'786 (95%)
RepeatMasker(ref)	622'184'946	2'273'364'079 (79%)	1'295'118'187	1'627'695'059 (56%)
Mappability(ref)	580'144'885	2'315'404'140 (80%)	273'776'835	2'649'036'411 (91%)
ExcessHeterozygosity	49'862'593	2'845'686'432 (98%)	138'264'407	2'784'548'839 (95%)
Depth (375<x<median * 1.5)	1'246'315'525	1'649'233'500 (57%)	1'355'482'338	1'567'330'908 (54%)
All_combined (all scaffolds)	1'748'758'452	114'6790'573 (40%)	1'991'560'501	931'252'745 (32%)
All_combined (with scaffolds length > 100kb)	1'775'681'421	1'119'867'604 (39%)	-	-
All_combined (with Goat only include 29 Chr)	-	-	2'003'874'943	918'938'303 (31%)

Supplementary Table 4. Summary table with distance to potential pedigrees and summary indices using the recent admixture inference method (Garcia-Erill et al. 2023) applied to all admixed samples identified by NGSAdmix assuming K=10. The “admixture index” can be interpreted as the number of generations since admixture, and is only shown for samples verified to be the result of recent admixture using this method. The “Distance to pedigree x” is the Jensen-Shannon distance of the estimated proportions to the expected under an independent pedigree, and to the pedigree identified as the most compatible recent admixture pedigrees. The bootstrap support indicates the percentage of bootstrap replicates where the pedigree has the lowest distance to the bootstrap estimate.

SampleID	Inconsistency Index	Distance to independent pedigree (bootstrap support)	Distance to pedigree 1 (bootstrap support)	Distance to pedigree 2 (bootstrap support)	Admixture index
415_Samburu	0.01	0.23 (0 %)	0.06 (98 %)	0.09 (2%)	3.56
2535_Luangwa	0.00	0.28 (0 %)	0.05 (100 %)	0.08 (0 %)	4.99
1133_QENP	0.00	0.20 (0 %)	0.01 (100 %)	0.25 (0 %)	4.02
393_Samburu	0.01	0.23 (0 %)	0.04 (100 %)	0.10 (0 %)	3.65
427_Nairobi	0.09	0.50 (0 %)	0.15 (87 %)	0.16 (13 %)	4.9
2994_Ugalla	0.17	0.03 (100 %)	0.25 (0 %)	0.25 (0 %)	
2996_Ugalla	0.01	0.20 (5 %)	0.11 (95 %)	0.19 (0 %)	4.21
392_Samburu	0.01	0.27 (2 %)	0.04 (95 %)	0.23 (3 %)	4.33

			%)		
398_Samburu	0.00	0.29 (0 %)	0.02 (100 %)	0.11 (0 %)	2.96
429_Nairobi	0.03	0.33 (0 %)	0.06 (69 %)	0.06 (31 %)	2.68
408_Samburu	0.00	0.23 (0 %)	0.06 (100 %)	0.09 (0 %)	3.56

Supplementary Table 5. Inferred parameters of demographic history between defassa and common waterbuck under a simple demographic model of population divergence without gene flow (NULL-model). We assumed a mutation rate of $1.43e-8$ per site per generation and 7.1 years of generation time.

Parameters				Point estimation
Effective population sizes	Ancestor	Common(Matetsi)& Defassa(Samole)	NANC	98762
	Population	Common(Matetsi)	NPOPC	39702
		Defassa(Samole)	NPOPD	43394
Time	Divergence	Common(Matetsi)& Defassa(Samole)	TDIV	253293

Supplementary Table 6. Inferred parameters of demographic history between defassa and common waterbuck under the best model with continuous gene flow from divergence to the

present (IM-model). We assumed a mutation rate of $1.43\text{e-}8$ per site per generation and 7.1 years of generation time.

Parameters				Point estimation	Standard Error ^a	
					Lower bound	Upper bound
Effective population sizes	Ancestor	Common(Matetsi)& Defassa(Sa mole)	NANC	87749	65165	110333
	Population	Common(Matetsi)	NPOPC	35939	23720	48159
		Defassa(Sa mole)	NPOPD	60833	42731	78935
Time	Divergence	Common(Matetsi)& Defassa(Sa mole)	TDIV	743136	311431	1174841
Migration rates		Defassa(Sa mole) to Common(Matetsi)	mDC	$6.06597\text{e-}06$	$2.428334\text{e-}06$	$9.703606\text{e-}06$
		Common(Matetsi) to	mCD	$8.8347\text{e-}07$	$-5.751769\text{e-}07$	$2.342117\text{e-}06$

	Defassa(Sa mole)				
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^aJackknife estimates obtained by 100 resampled SFS with same parameters setting up for the original data sets.

Supplementary Table 7. Inferred parameters of demographic history between defassa and common waterbuck under a model with temporary gene flow following divergence (MStop-model). We assumed a mutation rate of 1.43e-8 per site per generation and 7.1 years of generation time.

Parameters				Point estimation
Effective population sizes	Ancestor	Common(Matetsi)& Defassa(Samole)	NANC	87681
		Common(Matetsi)	NPOPNC	36473
		Defassa(Samole)	NPOPND	59810
	Population	Common(Matetsi)	NPOPC	85277
		Defassa(Samole)	NPOPD	92561
	Time	Divergence	Common(Matetsi)& Defassa(Samole)	TDIV
Common(Matetsi)& Defassa(Samole)			TMSTOP	8307
Migration rates		Defassa(Samole) to Common(Matetsi)	mDC	6.00448e-06
		Common(Matetsi) to Defassa(Samole)	mCD	9.36061e-07

Supplementary Table 8. Summary statistics for 14 Fst outlier windows.

Divergence island	Position	Twisst (quantile)	Pairwise diversity (quantile)	Pairwise diversity (Defassa)	Tajima's D (Common)	Tajima's D (Defassa)	LD (Common)	LD (Defassa)	Haplotype frequency ^a
Chr2 (NC_030809.1)	13470000-13590000	1.000	0.0426	0.0685	0.0474	0.0815	0.893	0.921	0.611
Chr5 (NC_030812.1)	55400000-55500000	1.000	0.0105	0.0165	0.00673	0.0661	0.749	0.941	-
Chr6 (NC_030813.1)	400000-1000000	0.881	0.193	0.00914	0.215	0.00341	0.0310	-	0.347
Chr7 (NC_030814.1)	56200000-56300000	0.941	0.0289	0.0687	0.0190	0.0907	0.715	0.982	0.384
Chr13 (NC_030820.1)	22400000-22500000	0.818	0.0501	0.0751	0.0204	0.0675	0.910	0.977	0.389
Chr14 (NC_030821.1)	26500000-26600000	0.810	0.0557	0.133	0.0411	0.161	0.992	0.0407	0.412
Chr16 (NC_030823.1)	41400000-41500000	1.000	0.0884	0.0308	0.0474	0.00810	0.879	0.736	-
Chr16 (NC_030823.1)	43200000-43300000	0.851	0.00254	0.00104	0.00175	0.000623	0.926	0.982	0.380
Chr16	49300000	0.962	0.00985	0.0460	0.00116	0.0168	0.964	0.980	0.384

(NC_030823.1)	-4960000 0								
Chr17 (NC_030824.1)	35800000 -3600000 0	0.965	0.00557	0.0856	0.00116	0.173	0.986	0.355	0.435
Chr18 (NC_030825.1)	38300000 -3930000 0	0.929	0.0133	0.0159	0.0184	0.0225	0.910	0.943	-
Chr22 (NC_030829.1)	17000000 -1710000 0	1.000	0.00212	0.0298	0.00237	0.0312	0.886	0.980	-
Chr25 (NC_030832.1)	1100000- 1700000	1.000	0.0354	0.0168	0.0190	0.00578	0.869	0.976	-
Chr25 (NC_030832.1)	3200000- 3300000	0.961	0.00262	0.000790	0.00378	0.00112	0.965	0.994	0.611

^a The “haplotype” frequency was only calculated for windows showing three distinct clusters.